

PROS AND CONS OF USING MOBILE PHONE IN PUPILS LIFE

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Annotation: *In addition to paying special attention to the protection of young people from various foreign spiritual, moral, political and religious ideas, regardless of the type of society, young people have been taught to sort information through their own logical reasoning. The creation of the mobile phone is a real revolution in technical development. But all technical progress has its downsides. For example, mobile phone is harmful to human health. This article provides information about Pros and cons of using mobile phone in pupils life.*

Key words: *Mobile addiction, phone, positive and negative sides, Internet, mobile education.*

In today's world, mobile phones are a necessity. Almost every young student has access to one and it is a tool that has changed the way education works as well. The digital world can be a lot to adjust to. Smart phones, the internet, social media, unlimited resources – all can seem a bit overwhelming, but at the same time, these things are indispensable. Since the day when our country gained independence, a lot of great work has been done to educate the young generation to be spiritually mature and perfect in all aspects. One of them, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, dated August 14, 2018, "On the measures to raise the youth spiritually, morally, and physically, and raise the quality of their education system to a new level" decision can be an example. Especially in the process of globalization, the importance of spiritual and moral education, specific to our national values, is increasing more and more. Although the concept of globalization was first used in 1933 by the British economist Fother in his article on the distribution and use of resources, the inevitable impact of globalization is felt in all components of global life.

There are several advantages and disadvantages for the child during their school-age. Such as online study, offline study, use of technology, educational board, and many more. Similarly, there are other advantages and disadvantages for the child during school-age and that is the use of cell phones for students. In the growing technology, we can see that the cell phone is one of the most desired and essential

elements for human life. It becomes one of the most integral parts of human life. Therefore, we mostly depend on the cell phone in our daily life. There are several advantages and disadvantages of cell phones for students. It also provides a huge impact on school-age children. According to the best school in howrah, the cell phone is provided a different impression to the child and parents. Let's discuss things in detail. They also must go through school staff whenever they need to communicate with their parents. Allowing cell phones in schools empowers students to use their phones to access educational apps, get quick answers to research questions, record any negative events that take place during the school day, and reach out to parents or guardians for assistance. In addition, a situation where cell phones are allowed encourages students and teachers to work together to create policies that ensure phones don't cause distractions. Unrestricted cell phone use in schools can make cheating easier. There are many ways that this can happen. One is that students will access information using their phones during a test. In addition, students can potentially text answers back and forth during tests. Finally, a student may be motivated to snap photos of a test as a way to make money by selling snapshots of tests to students. While cell phones can keep students socially connected in a positive way, they can also encourage negative communications. A student will have no place of refuge from bullying if peers are exchanging messages, posts, and photos all day long. School can be a valuable setting for disconnecting from technology while interacting with the "real world." Multiple studies have found that an increase in use of a mobile phone can result in negative psychological consequences. This includes higher rates of anxiety, depression, fatigue, and exhaustion.

In addition to decreasing overall well-being, the negative effects of technology use may also decrease academic ability. Needless to say, having access to a mobile phone has a massive effect on student life and their educational journey. Like any invention, mobile phones have a good side and a bad. Both of these sides need to be kept in mind, as one tries to understand the extent of impact mobile phones have had on student life. Here are some good and bad ways in which mobile phones have affected students: The biggest advantage of the mobile phone is the ease of communication. Students can have 24/7 access to their peers, their teachers, their parents, and their friends, meaning that any doubt to be solved or information to be shared can be done in a matter of minutes. This is especially useful during stressful exam times or when students have absenteeism, since they can easily catch up on the work they missed. Security and safety of students is another major positive effect of the mobile phone. Through location services and texts or phone calls, parents and teachers can be assured that students are safe and secure at all times. Going to extra

classes, taking part in co-curriculars, going out of town on a school trip, etc. has never been more stress free. Mobile phones have brought the world into our homes. For students, smartphones represent the endless world of knowledge, at their fingertips. All the information and technology that a student could possibly need, is easily accessible to them at all times, making the process of study much more streamlined and effective. Mobile phones have also brought convenience and accessibility to the classroom. Earlier, students that did not have a computer could not research online or avail the services of the internet. However, with smartphones, students have the internet with them all the time, meaning that studying or researching online is extremely fast and convenient. Mobile phones also have a big role in time management and organisation in a student's life. Apps like notepads, alarms, reminders, calendars, digital organisers and list-makers help students keep their academic and extra-curricular life on track. They can ensure they never miss an assignment deadline or forget an exam date. Apart from aiding students in studying, mobile phones also play a huge role in keeping them stress-free and allowing them some much needed relaxation. Through mobiles, students can listen to music, read books, watch movies, pick up new hobbies, listen to podcasts, play games, connect with their friends and basically partake in activities that will take their mind off work, and give them some time to rejuvenate.

Negative Effects of Mobile Phones on Students

There is no denying that the biggest distractions in a student's life comes from the smartphone. A phone offers numerous channels where students can spend time, without even realising how much time is being wasted. Social media, movie streaming platforms, gaming, etc. are all serious distractions that can affect a student's school life and academic performance severely. Mobile phones also come with certain health risks. The blue light of mobile screens have been known to cause problems with eyesight. Similarly, radiation from phones can be harmful for some children. Apart from this, lack of physical exercise, sleep deprivation, headaches are also some health issues that are associated with mobile phone usage. One of the biggest perils of mobile phones is the access they provide to social media platforms. Excessive use of social media has been linked not only with physical health issues but also serious mental and emotional health disorders. Social media addiction, cyberbullying, body image issues, depression, anxiety, alienation, etc. are some of the issues that social media and therefore, smartphones are responsible for in young children. Since mobile phones bring a world of resources to your fingertips, it also leads to certain resources that are not reliable. Mobile phones can expose students to unreliable sources, misinformation, propaganda, inappropriate content and other such things that can also harm their academic and personal lives to a large extent.

Mobile addiction - this problem was first raised a few years ago, but now with 7 out of 10 people in developed countries having a mobile phone, this problem has become a real epidemic. It is difficult to separate habit and addiction in mobile communication, but it is possible, maybe necessary, necessary. Mobile addiction is a human condition, in which the phone becomes an object of worship, a person calls without thinking, does not understand his action, or cannot explain the reason. Mobile addiction is like internet addiction. This is the fear of live communication and the fact that there is nothing in the real world that causes positive emotions in a person, and a person tries to get positive emotions through the Internet or over the phone.

How to know if you have mobile addiction. - Constantly reaching for the phone. When an unpleasant situation arises (an unexpected interlocutor appears, a person you don't like, touching on a sensitive topic in a conversation), a person hides himself from the world around him with a phone. He takes the phone just to check the account, read or send SMS, press buttons, see the time. All these actions are a human response to an unfavorable situation. A person avoids a problem instead of finding a solution. - Changing the phone frequently. Today, we can observe people who change their phones faster than they change their gloves. A phone that a person likes can be replaced by the same phone with only one or two new functions, for which a person is ready for anything and buys this phone. A person who uses a phone for communication does not look for its new models, if the available functions are enough for him, on the contrary, a person who depends on the phone looks for a new one. - Call for call. It is not good if the number of "just" junk calls is more than the number of calls that are important and necessary. - SMS to SMS. In practice, it is like a "call for a call", a person can call a friend who is ten meters away (even if it is easier to go to him). Some people prefer to communicate via SMS rather than verbal communication. Conversations about "phones" and communication. The submissive turns the topic into a "favorite" topic, enjoys discussing phone models, data plans, and other signs of mobile culture.

There are many reasons for the emergence of mobile addiction, as mentioned earlier, it is a lack of self-confidence that leads to the desire to stand out from the crowd and show off, but someone is suffering from being alone, and this person calls the phone his "little friend". not even for a minute. This is not scary, it is observed that only one person out of a hundred can understand it, and no one voluntarily tries to fight it, and the important thing is that a person cannot fight it alone. We can't even go out to buy bread for five minutes without a mobile phone, thinking that "I might miss the most important call at this moment." Who will tell people about these problems, after all, everyone around them is addicted to the phone?! It is possible and necessary to fight, for this you need to pay a little attention to look at yourself from the outside and

find out the reason that gives you permission to lose the attachment to the phone. Learn to turn off your phone at night, put it in your pocket when you're not using it, you don't have to show it to everyone, because other people's phones are no less than yours. But the most important thing is to turn off the phone when you are resting, even if it is bedtime after lunch. Turn it off during class, during a meeting, during a meeting with friends, and most importantly, don't forget to warn your loved ones about it! They may worry about you during this period. It's even easier when it comes to technical dependence, in which "do I really need these features on the phone that I only need to make calls?" ask yourself! The success of work depends on the correct use of things - use a computer to connect to the Internet, make calls from a home phone, listen to music on a tape recorder, and watch movies on TV or in a theater.

The light emitted from a mobile phone seriously affects human brain cells and exposes it to various dangerous diseases. But today, the phone has become one of the most important tools in the life of our teenagers. Phones do not fall out of the hands of young men and women on the streets. True, now is the age of technology, the possibilities of technology are endless. Sometimes even adults talk on the phone for hours. In fact, 4 minutes are enough to know the health of the other party when using the phone. We are used to unlimited Internet and unlimited phone options, and we are indifferent to the events around us. In the virtual world, we talk for hours with our acquaintances, at least in the virtual world we love and make friends, we destroy our flower-like family through relationships with these "friends". Currently, the number of mobile subscribers in the world is 1.9 billion. Almost every second person in our country has a mobile phone. A person using a mobile phone will not feel its effect for 15 seconds. If you increase the time of talking and use, then you will notice a clear change, because the alpha waves deteriorate the brain activity and start to show its wave properties. The most sensitive part of the human body to electromagnetic radiation is the head, and it is in this area that the conversation is conducted. Therefore, it further increases the acceleration of the radiation process in a person. When experts measure a person's blood pressure during a conversation, it was found that the pressure rises at different ages. It should be noted that one out of every 20 people in the world becomes a victim of this mobile communication radiation. In 2000, the World Health Organization, in a report presented to the European Parliament on the harm of mobile phones, stated that the influence of mobile phones on people's cancer is strong. When German experts conducted electromagnetic radiation tests on cell phones with and without a camera, the radiation from camera phones was higher than that from plain cell phones. Radiation is mainly emitted by a mobile phone during a conversation, but

in the "standby" state, it is not completely free from radiation, because the mobile phone tells the base station that it is within its network, receiving calls, SMS, etc.

informs about readiness. It will be useful for users who put an "alarm clock" on their mobile phone at night and take it with them to know. As for the procedure for using the mobile phone, it is better to hold it in the hand, not in the "standby" position during the conversation. It is also important to turn off in the metro, outside the service area, at night, at unnecessary times, if not necessary. In addition, it is not recommended to carry it inside the outer clothing. It should be carried as much as possible in the hand and side bag. Cell phones should also be kept away from young children. The International Agency for Research on Cancer and the World Health Organization have recognized for the first time that mobile phones cause dangerous tumors in people. Until now, only assumptions have been made about it, but now influential international organizations have expressed their opinion about the harm of mobile phones. Electromagnetic waves have always been considered harmful to health. If it is directed directly into the ear every day, the effect on the nerve tissue that provides the function of the internal organs of hearing and vision (eyeball) shows. Some people don't take their mobile phones away from their ears for hours a day. It is extremely difficult for the body.

Damage to brain tissue, according to some researchers, is clearly manifested not immediately, but only after 15-20 years. Therefore, they believe that in the near future the number of people with brain tumors will increase dramatically. Because just 15 minutes of talking on a cell phone every day is enough to cause brain cancer. So, if we moderate the use of such electromagnetic radiation-producing devices, we will protect our health and that of our offspring.

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